

Review Article about Ventilator

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Abstract:

Ventilators support patients who cannot breathe properly on their own and thus have a crucial role in the management of patients experiencing respiratory failure. Indeed, the number of patients needing ventilatory support is considerable. Consequently, saving lives by improving ventilators is an overarching goal. This review paper discusses the functionality of the devices to make them life-like, information guiding the adjustment of ventilators during therapeutic procedures, control systems enabling automatic tuning of ventilators, and evaluates how these technologies can be further

improved. The focus is here on systems that directly transfer energy to the respiratory system. This includes not only positive pressure generators but also life support systems that apply negative pressures. Life-supporting ventilators that do not transfer any energy are beyond the focus, such as gas delivery systems that increase the oxygen concentration in natural or simulated in vitro lungs, which do not help the patient but the development of potentially better ventilators. We envision that the field still has many unsolved issues offering substantial scientific challenges that will keep researchers in respiratory mechanics occupied for many decades to come.

Keywords: *Review, Ventilator, patients.*

Introduction

When we are healthy, we take our breath for granted, never appreciating the vitality of our lungs. But when our lung health is impaired, we care about nothing more than breathing in the world. This is the painful reality for those suffering from lung disease, which affects people of all ages in every corner of the world. Lung disease kills millions and causes suffering to millions more. The threats to our lung health are everywhere, and they start at a young age, when we are most vulnerable. Fortunately, many of these threats can be prevented and their consequences treated. If we start acting now, we can save lives and prevent suffering around the world.

You may have heard that some people have difficulty getting off a ventilator. There are two possible reasons for this:

- 1) The underlying problem hasn't gotten better.
- 2) The strength of the breathing muscles has decreased due to disuse.

Ideally, a person needs a ventilator for only a short time until the problem goes away. For example, until an overdose wears off or medications stop an asthma attack. But some problems don't go away. For example, a person with brain damage from a severe stroke or injury may not get better enough to get off a ventilator.

If a person is on a ventilator for a long time, their breathing muscles may become weaker. In this

case, doctors strengthen the muscles by having the person breathe on their own for a short time each day. This helps gradually increase the strength of their breathing until the person can get off the ventilator. Respiratory diseases are a burden

200 million people have chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), 65 million people have moderate to severe COPD, 1-6% of the adult population (more than 100 million people) suffer from sleep apnea, 7.8 million people suffer from pulmonary hypertension, more than 50 million people struggle with occupational lung disease, 1 billion people develop tuberculosis each year, totaling more than 1 billion people suffer from chronic respiratory disease. At least 2 billion people are exposed to the toxic effects of biomass fuel consumption, 1 billion people are exposed to air pollution in public places and 1 billion more are exposed to tobacco smoke. Each year, 4 million people die prematurely from chronic respiratory diseases, and lung diseases, especially for infants and young children, are particularly vulnerable. Nine million children under 5 years of age die each year, the most common cause of these deaths. Pneumonia is the biggest killer of children. Children in the world Asthma is the most common chronic disease and there are several main causes of respiratory arrest, the most important of which are suffocation, drowning, electric shock, and many other conditions that lead to respiratory arrest.

History

The Greek physician Galen (129–200 AD) may have been the first to describe artificial ventilation: "If you take a dead animal and force air through its throat (through a trachea), the trachea will fill up and you will see the lungs in a state of great swelling." The Flemish physician Andreas Vesalius (1514–1564) also describes ventilation by inserting a trachea into the trachea of animals. In 1773, the English physician William House (1736–1808) began to promote the ability of artificial respiration to revive people who had apparently drowned. For a year he paid a reward out of his own pocket to

anyone who brought him a drowned person who had been rescued from the water within a reasonable time of drowning. Thomas Cogan (1736–1818), another English physician, became interested in the same subject during his stay in Amsterdam, where an institute for the preservation of life from accidents in the water had been founded in 1767, and he joined House. In the summer of 1774 House and Cogan gathered fifteen friends to meet in a coffee house called the Chapter where they founded the Royal Humane Society as a group to promote first aid and resuscitation. Some of the methods and equipment were similar to those used today, such as wooden pipes inserted into victims' nostrils to force air into the lungs. Others, such as bellows and a flexible tube used to force tobacco smoke through the anus to revive vestigial (non-functional) life in the victim's intestines, eventually fell out of use as more was understood about the process.

Ventilator: It is a device that performs breathing movements on behalf of the patient and forces him to breathe, without which the patient's condition would lead to death. The process is called mechanical ventilation. The ventilator uses pressure to push air into the lungs. The air is usually mixed with pure oxygen, so it contains a larger amount of oxygen compared to what is in the room air. Doctors adjust the ventilator to control the number of breaths and the amount of air it gets each time. The ventilator can perform all breathing movements or just help the patient do them. There are several important things that must be verified before starting the artificial respiration process, which are:

- 1) The injured person's pulse must be checked (by feeling the heartbeats). If the pulse is absent, first aid is performed to restore the heart's function by massaging it externally.
- 2) It must be checked that there is no foreign body inside the mouth or blocking the upper respiratory passages before starting the artificial respiration process.
- 3) It is prohibited to perform artificial respiration on an injured person who is still breathing.

Because respiratory failure can be fatal, mechanical ventilation systems are considered essential to life, and precautions must be taken to ensure their reliability, including their power supply.

Therefore, mechanical ventilation systems are carefully designed so that no single loophole can put the patient at risk. They may have manual backup mechanisms to enable manual breathing in the absence of power (such as the ventilator built into an anesthesia machine). They are also equipped with safety valves, which open to the atmosphere in the absence of power to act as an anti-suffocation valve, and the patient breathes automatically. Some systems are also equipped with compressed gas tanks, air compressors, or backup batteries to provide ventilation in the event of a power failure or faulty gas supply, and also have methods of operation or calling for help in the event of failure of their mechanisms or software.

The patient needs a ventilator in the following cases:

- 1) Inability to breathe.
- 2) When breathing is very weak.

Inability to breathe or weak breathing can result from many causes, including:

- 1) Brain problems: such as stroke and head injury;
- 2) Lung problems: asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), severe pneumonia;
- 3) Heart problems: heart attack, heart failure;
- 4) Nerve problems: spinal cord injury, myasthenia gravis;
- 5) Generalized problems in the body: drug overdose, poisoning, severe trauma

There are many cases in which a ventilator is used.

1. Respiratory failure

Respiratory failure is an emergency condition characterized by difficulty breathing, accumulation of carbon dioxide in the blood, and the body's organs not getting enough oxygen

The following points answer the question of when to use a ventilator? In case of respiratory failure:

- 1) Acute respiratory failure syndrome.
- 2) Strokes or head injuries.
- 3) Asthma or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.
- 4) Respiratory distress syndrome in newborns.
- 5) Pneumonia.
- 6) Sepsis.
- 7) Sudden cardiac arrest.
- 8) Diseases that affect the nerves and muscles that control breathing, such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, polio, myasthenia gravis, various spinal cord injuries, cases of overdose of some medications or drugs.

2. Surgery

Surgery is also an answer to the question of when to use artificial respiration? Because performing surgeries requires general anesthesia, which in turn can affect the breathing process.

The Artificial Ventilator consists of two main parts. The first is mechanical or pneumatic and is responsible for providing the patient with the required amount of air. So that it consists of:

- 1) A set of air tubes that allow air to enter and exit, to form what is called the respiratory circuit.
- 2) A set of valves or regulators that control the entry and exit of air.
- 3) Air Filters which purify oxygen and gases from impurities and are characterized by having a specific lifespan and must be cleaned continuously.
- 4) Humidifier which enables the doctor to control the humidity and temperature of the gases entering the patient.

The second part which is the most important is electronic part which performs continuous monitoring and comparison of the most important characteristics of the incoming and outgoing air through the artificial respiration process (Pressure

+ Volume + Flow rate + Temperature) with the values entered by the doctor on the device by using specialized sensors. Sensors for each type of these factors, as there are alarm signals. Alarms are made to warn when there is any malfunction in the electronic system or when there is a leak in the respiratory circuit.

This part also consists of:

- 1) Timing Unit;
- 2) Power Supply;
- 3) Regulation Unit.

By specifying a specific percentage for each of them from the time of the respiratory cycle to control the transition from one stage to another.

Time Controlled Ventilators

In some other types of ventilators, the process of controlling both inhalation and exhalation is done by setting a specific air pressure.

Pressure controlled at which the transition between the two stages takes place or a specific air volume may be set.

Volume controlled in order to control the patient's respiratory cycle.

In all these types, the signal is converted into an electrical signal to facilitate its loading and handling by the control unit in the device.

How a Ventilator Works?

There are two ways that ventilators can get air into the lungs:

- 1) Through a plastic tube inserted into the windpipe (called invasive ventilation, because the tube "invades" the body);
- 2) Through a face mask that fits tightly over the face (called noninvasive ventilation).

Invasive ventilation is used for people who need the most help breathing. Doctors can insert the tube into the windpipe through the mouth (the most common way) and the nose.

A small incision in the front of the neck (a procedure called a tracheostomy). You will have a tracheostomy if you need to be on a ventilator

for more than a few days. The tracheostomy tube is inserted into the windpipe below the voice box. This way, the tube won't press on the vocal cords, thus avoiding damage to them.

Having a tube in your nose or throat can be uncomfortable, so you'll be given medication through an IV to keep you relaxed and comfortable.

Noninvasive ventilation is used if the patient is awake and breathing well on their own, but needs some help. If the person is unconscious or very weak, noninvasive ventilation is not helpful. This is because the tongue retracts into the throat and blocks the air coming from the face mask. With both invasive and noninvasive ventilation, doctors program the ventilator so that the patient gets the right amount of oxygen and the right number of breaths. The ventilator can tell if the patient is able to breathe a little on their own, and then adjusts to help them breathe only.

How to Connect the Ventilator?

- 1) Connect the device to the electricity source, then press the start button.
- 2) Connect the device hoses to the oxygen O₂ and air source located in the wall. There are devices that have only one connection, which is the oxygen O₂ connection only.
- 3) Connect the connections (hoses) to the device and make sure that there are no bends or leaks in the connections or in the device because this will stop the device from working.

Benefits of the Ventilator

After answering the question of when is ventilator used? We must know that ventilator is used for a temporary period that is calculated based on specific factors specific to the patient until the desired benefit from ventilator is obtained

Among the benefits of ventilator, we mention the following points:

- Providing comfort to the patient's respiratory muscles, as he does not have to exert great effort in breathing.

- Giving the patient the necessary time until he regains his natural ability to breathe.
- Providing the body with the necessary oxygen and getting rid of carbon dioxide.
- Maintaining a regular airway, which prevents various injuries.

Risks of Artificial Respiration

There are a number of risks that may sometimes result from artificial respiration, and among these potential risks we mention the following:

1. Infections

Artificial respiration may lead to the risk of contracting various infections even if there is a respiratory infection before using artificial respiration, and the patient may contract infections through the following points:

- the possibility of bacteria entering through the breathing tube, which may cause inflammation in the air sacs in the lungs;
- the breathing tube may cause difficulty in coughing, which helps get rid of waste in the lungs, which leads to irritation and inflammation of the lungs.

2. Lung collapse

Atelectasis results when the lung or parts of the lung are unable to expand normally, which leads to the collapse of the air sacs and reduces the amount of oxygen entering the blood.

3. Lung damage

Lung damage may result from several things, such as: providing the patient with more oxygen than he needs or for a longer period than necessary or if the air force is greater than necessary, especially when there is weakness in the lungs. Among the conditions that may result from lung damage are the following: pneumothorax, pulmonary edema, hypoxemia.

4. Delirium

Medications accompanying artificial respiration may cause delirium accompanied by some temporary symptoms, such as: memory loss, difficulty sleeping, reading, writing, and thinking clearly.

5. Inability to move

The inability to move resulting from anesthesia accompanying artificial respiration may cause several complications, including the following: bedsores, skin infections, blood clots, muscle weakness.

6. Vocal cord problems

Many vocal cord problems may result when the artificial respiration breathing tube is removed, such as: hoarseness of voice and pain.

Nursing role before placing the patient on the ventilator are:

Preparing tools:

- 1) Connect the device to the electricity source.
- 2) Connect the ventilator to the oxygen and air source.
- 3) Install the breathing hoses (connections) to the device.
- 4) Make sure there are no leaks in the hoses or the device. Turn on the device from the power switch on the back.
- 5) Connect the lung test and do by stand, then press the reset alarm button.
- 6) Prepare a tracheal tube - a laryngoscope.
- 7) Tube - Embolization with a mask - Airway - 10 cm syringe.
- 8) Section device - 2 suction catheter devices (for the mouth and the laryngeal tube - sterile water).
- 9) Gauze bandage - Plaster.
- 10) Gastric tube - Sterile gauze - Clean gauze - Sterile joint.

Possible complications of the ventilator are: pneumonia, sinus infections, lung damage, problems with perception and thinking, muscle weakness, blood clots and bedsores, damage to the vocal cords, airway obstructions, collapsed lungs, pneumothorax.

Ventilator Parameters

(1) VT (Tidal Volume)

The amount of air that enters the patient's lungs in one breath and is determined by multiplying*

the patient's weight by 6 or 8 and is usually 450:500.

(2) RR (Respiratory Rate)

The respiratory rate per minute.

(3) FiO₂

The fraction of inspired oxygen, FiO₂.

An estimate of the oxygen content that a person inhales the present of oxygen that is delivered to the lung.

It is the percentage of oxygen present in the air inside the lung.

Normal range/ 21% to 100%.

(4) PEEP (positive & Respiratory

It is the amount of air that remains inside the patient's lungs and is usually 5:10. When measuring CVP, we subtract peep from the measurement in the event that the patient is connected to a ventilator with me

It improves the oxygen level and preserves the alveoli.

1) If it exceeds 10, it means that the pressure inside the lung has increased.

It will reduce the amount of blood returning from the body and the patient may enter hypotension.

2) If a patient comes in an accident and has a head injury.

It is better to leave peep zero because if peep increases.

The blood returning from the brain will decrease and the pressure inside the brain will increase.

3) If a patient has a chest tube and I find that the chest tube is gurgling, meaning it makes bubbles, it is better to leave peep zero.

(5) Sensitivity/ Trigger

It is the effort required from the patient it works. To take a breath with the help of the vent device. The more the sense increases, the more the patient needs to exert more effort.

(6) Inspiratory to Expiratory Ratio

The ratio between the time of inspiration and the time of expiration.

N.Rang 1:2 / 1:1.5.

(7) Flow

The speed of air inside the lung

N.R 40:100 liters/minute.

Whenever oxygen exceeds 60%, it causes poisoning in the lungs, so it is not useful to leave the patient on 100% oxygen for more than an hour because it causes Oxygen Toxicity:

- By raising the oxygen to 100%.

Before doing suction and before any intervention that requires effort.

- And do not increase the suction for more than 10 or 15 seconds.

Problems that May Occur during Artificial Respiration

High air pressure

1_ Secretion airway (ETT).

High air pressure may be due to secretions that need to be suctioned.

2_ Kinked tube or ETT.

There is a bend in the device tubes or the tube.

3_ patient biting in ETT

The patient bites the tube, so we put an airway in his mouth.

4_ water in the ventilator tubing.

There is water in the device tubes, so empty this water.

5_ patient coughing.

The patient resists the device when he coughs.

6_ Bronchospasm.

Low air pressure

1_ Disconnected tubing.

Disconnect one of the ventilator tubes, so we connect it.

2_ Cuff Leak.

The ETT tube is not filled with air well.

3- Leak in Humidifier or tubing systems.

There is a leak in the tubing system

3 Apnea

The cessation of breathing is due to no spontaneous breath. In this case, we encourage the patient to take a breath or give a breath through the tube.

Oxygen Not Enough

The oxygen is insufficient or low.

Because the oxygen hose is not connected to the device or the network.

4 High Respiratory Rate

High respiratory rate is due to Patient Anxiety
Pain

Hypoxia Low oxygen levels

High temperature _Fever

5 Low Tidal Volume

Low amount of air entering the patient and is due to

The tubes are not connected together in a tight circuit

(We constantly check the connections)

Or the balloon for the ETT or Tracheostomy has a leak or is not filled with air, so the balloon must be filled sufficiently with air.

6 No Tidal Volume

No air entering the patient and is due to the ventilator device stops due to a malfunction, for example.

Or one of the tubes is disconnected from each other

As if it is not connected to the ETT or Tracheostomy tube

Or a power outage

The patient must be constantly monitored to ensure the integrity of the connections and that no problem occurs.

How to choose a ventilator

A ventilator is chosen based on the need for it, as the amount of risk to which a person is exposed is measured to determine the type of device he needs. The most important things to consider when choosing a ventilator are: identifying and controlling risks, exposure assessment, selecting a ventilator, training program for using a ventilator, inspection and record keeping, cleaning and sterilizing ventilators, repairing and maintaining ventilators, proper storage of ventilators, health monitoring, physical fitness should be checked.

Conclusions

A very useful and important device to help people with tired lungs.

A safe device to use and has no side effects.

An environmentally friendly device made of nanomaterials that are not effective over time.

It is used to reduce oxygen deficiency in all parts and organs of the body.

The presence of this device helped us a lot in light of the Covid 19 pandemic. It helps a patient who is unable to breathe and saves him from death.

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